

2. Amrein-Beardsley, A., & Holloway, J. (2017). Value-added models for teacher evaluation and accountability: Commonsense assumptions, *Educational Policy*, 33(3), 516-542.
3. Ballou, D., & Springer, M. G. (2015). Using student test scores to measure teacher performance. *Educational Researcher*, 44(2), 77-86.
4. Ballou, D., Sanders, W., & Wright, P. (2004). Controlling for student background in value-added assessment of teachers. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, 29(1), 37-65.
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THE THEORY OF PROBLEM-SOLVING TASKS IN TEACHING TO THE PRIMARY LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** This article explores the specific features of problem-solving activities and their importance for primary school students. Problem-solving activities help children develop critical thinking, self-confidence, and the ability to express freely their opinions on events that they may encounter in learning foreign languages. In addition, conducting problem-solving activities with a large group of children helps them develop teamwork and listening skills objectives.*

***Keywords.** Problem-solving, critical thinking, features, activities, teamwork, primary school, conduct, ability, importance.*

Introduction: In the educational process, skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving are aimed at helping primary school children easily learn lessons, especially new languages. Working with children who have independent thinking and can find solutions to any problem has a great impact on the teacher, making

the teaching process more interesting and meaningful. Problem-solving also includes attitudinal and cognitive components. To solve problems, learners have to want to do so, and they have to believe they can. Motivation and attitudinal aspects such as effort, confidence, anxiety, persistence, and knowledge about self are important to the problem-solving process (Jonassen and Tessmer, 1996) (1). Problem solving changed to reflect a complex mental activity including a range of cognitive abilities and activities because of the influence of cognitive learning theories. Higher-level cognitive abilities including "visualization, association, abstraction, comprehension, manipulation, reasoning, analysis, synthesis, and generalization—each needing to be 'managed' and 'coordinated'" were all part of problem-solving.

The use of authentic materials for 7-10-year-old children

Definition of Authentic Materials - The term authentic materials has been defined in different ways throughout the literature. Nunan (1989, as cited in Adams, 1995) states that authentic materials are not always produced for language teaching. Authentic materials also provide a platform for developing critical thinking and analytical skills, as students are encouraged to interpret and analyze the content meaningfully. By incorporating materials that students find relevant and interesting, educators can create a more dynamic and interactive classroom environment that fosters active learning (2). Authentic materials expose learners to the language as native speakers naturally use it. This exposure includes slang, idiomatic expressions, and varied sentence structures often missing in traditional textbooks (Gilmore, 2007). By interacting with these materials, learners develop a more comprehensive understanding of the language, enhancing their ability to use it accurately and appropriately in real-life situations (3).

Authentic materials for the English language classroom are often free and very easy to find online or perhaps in certain locations in your communities. Here are some examples:

- TV shows, news segments, documentaries, movie clips and trailers, online videos, and commercials

- Radio broadcasts, songs, and podcasts
- Photographs, artwork, signs, postcards, maps, and advertisements
- Magazines, letters and emails, news articles, brochures, websites, blogs, and social media posts
- Recipes, food labels, bus and train schedules, menus, price tags, and product descriptions (4).

Authentic materials are beneficial because they show a real-world use of language and often present content that is of high interest to students. Most authentic materials present current topics in news or culture or help students learn information that is useful in their everyday lives. For this reason, using authentic materials often increases students' motivation and willingness to take risks with English. Real materials, unlike materials made specifically for teaching, are not created with certain grammatical structures or vocabulary in mind. Instead, they provide an opportunity for students (5).

Specific features of the problem-solving activities

Foreign language as a school subject is skill-oriented. Thus, the problem-solving approach applied to it implies different components than when it is applied to subjects that are knowledge-oriented (e.g. history) (6). My own experience dealing with kids and their psychological state at a summer camp for kids has informed me of the importance of problem-solving exercises for schoolchildren between the ages of 7 and 10. My research and competence have demonstrated the following findings about the relevance of creating problem-solving exercises for language learning for children, in that -being able to think independently while learning a language;

-children learning a language in a free atmosphere in a way that's suitable for them (singing, communicating, watching cartoons or video games);

-being able to work successfully in a team environment;

-obtaining the skill to compare their native language with the foreign language they are learning;

-developing powerful capacities for critical thinking by sharing thoughts with others.

Conclusion. The realization that problem-solving in foreign language teaching is a time-consuming process both on the teacher's (planning, materials selection) and the learner's (arriving at a solution) part. (7). It is an intellectually demanding approach for both teachers and learners, too. But this approach is indispensable if we want our learners not only to have essential knowledge, which today very quickly becomes outdated but also to have the skills to acquire knowledge incessantly. This idea of various authors (Barrows, 1980, Botti & Myers, 1995, etc.) was supported by our research as well.

REFERENCES

1. <https://americanenglish.state.gov/resources/teachers-corner-teaching-authentic-materials>
2. <https://americanenglish.state.gov/resources/teachers-corner-teaching-authentic-materials>
3. <https://eflcafe.net/using-authentic-materials-to-teach-english/>
4. <https://eflcafe.net/using-authentic-materials-to-teach-english/>
5. Jamie Kirkley, "Principles for Teaching Problem Solving", Indiana University, 2003. Pg.5.
6. "Problem-solving in teaching foreign languages to students of pedagogical departments" by Natela DOGHONADZE and Gulnara GORGILADZE. Pg.103. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227439803_Problem_Solving_in_Teaching_Foreign_Languages_to_Students_of_Pedagogical_Departments
7. "Problem-solving in teaching foreign languages to students of pedagogical departments" by Natela DOGHONADZE and Gulnara GORGILADZE. Pg.113. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227439803_Problem_Solving_in_Teaching_Foreign_Languages_to_Students_of_Pedagogical_Departments